

A Study of Clinical Outcomes of Pediatric Penetrating Keratoplasty at a Tertiary Eye Care Center

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Abstract:

Background: Penetrating keratoplasty in children is a complex and demanding procedure, often carrying a high risk of graft failure or unsuccessful amblyopia treatment, even in cases with clear grafts. Despite these challenges, keratoplasty remains the preferred surgical option for managing pediatric corneal stromal opacities or edema. The current study was done to determine the indications and clinical outcomes of pediatric penetrating keratoplasty.

Methods: This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Sarojini Devi Eye Hospital, Osmania Medical College, Hyderabad. A detailed history was taken to determine the etiology of corneal insult, associated symptoms, and duration followed by a general examination, best corrected visual acuity using Snellens/ LogMAR charts, and slit-lamp biomicroscopy for anterior segment evaluation. Further, the patients were subjected to syringing for patency of lacrimal apparatus, and B scan ultrasound to rule out posterior segment pathologies.

Results: The most affected age group was 6-10 years, accounting for 40% of cases. The youngest (1-5 years) and oldest (16-18 years) age groups had the lowest representation. There was a slight male predominance, with males accounting for 55% of cases and females for 45%. The majority of patients (65%) experienced improved vision following PKP. A smaller proportion (20%) maintained unchanged visual acuity. A limited number of patients (15%) experienced either no assessable or worsened visual outcomes. The data suggests that PKP is generally effective in improving visual function in pediatric patients. Graft acceptance: 60% of cases (12 out of 20) demonstrated successful graft acceptance. 35% of cases (7 out of 20) experienced graft rejection. 5% of cases (1 out of 20) resulted in graft failure. Regarding surgical interventions, the majority of cases required a single grafting procedure.

Conclusion: In conclusion, penetrating keratoplasty is still the best operation that can be done in children with corneal opacities and ectasias because there are no other options available. Even though the process gives low potential for graft rejection and an average amount of vision enhancement, timely intervention, professional surgery, and adequate post-operative treatment can contribute much to positive results.

Keywords: Penetrating Pediatric Keratoplasty, Corneal Opacities, Allograft, Visual Outcome.

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Introduction

Penetrating keratoplasty in children is a highly challenging and demanding procedure associated with a high risk of graft failure or failure of amblyopia therapy in clear grafts. Nonetheless, keratoplasty remains the surgery for managing pediatric corneal stromal opacities or edema. Allograft rejection, graft infection, corneal neovascularization, glaucoma, trauma to the anterior segment, vitreous pathology, and additional surgical interventions, especially those related to glaucoma management, are important risk factors [1]. The incidence of pediatric PKP is estimated to be 2.9 to 3.5 per million children

annually, according to various studies conducted in different regions. Pediatric keratoplasty accounts for approximately 3-10% of all corneal transplants performed globally, with variations depending on the region and available eye care facilities. In developed countries, congenital corneal opacities and inherited corneal dystrophies are the most common indications for pediatric PKP, while in developing countries, acquired conditions like infectious keratitis and trauma are more frequent. The majority of pediatric PKP procedures are performed in children younger than 10 years old, with the highest incidence occurring in children

under 5 years of age. This is largely due to the early onset of congenital corneal opacities and the critical need for early intervention to prevent amblyopia.

Visual rehabilitation of pediatric-age patients is a major challenge for corneal transplant surgeons. Penetrating keratoplasty (PKP) is the only way to restore vision and prevent irreversible blindness due to amblyopia in children with irreversible corneal blinding pathologies. Performing penetrating corneal grafts in children poses difficulty in the evaluation, technical difficulties during surgery, and problems during follow-up. Younger children do not cooperate for proper slit-lamp examination and need to be examined under general anesthesia. Even after a successful graft, the child requires rigorous treatment for amblyopic treatment. Parents need to be counseled before surgery and possible visual outcomes and chances of obtaining a clear graft should be discussed. In addition, the complications encountered post-PKP, including allograft rejection, post-PKP astigmatism, and post-PKP glaucoma are more frequent in the pediatric group as compared to adult recipients [2]. The current study was done to determine the indications and clinical outcomes of pediatric penetrating keratoplasty.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Sarojini Devi Eye Hospital, Osmania Medical College, Hyderabad. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study after duly following the protocol for the research on Human subjects. Written consent was obtained from the parents/guardians for the study on children. Explanation of the procedure was done in the vernacular language. Patients with an age group less than 18 years with Acquired Corneal Opacity (traumatic/ non-traumatic) were targeted for the study.

A detailed history was taken to determine the etiology of corneal insult, associated symptoms, and duration followed by a general examination, best corrected visual acuity using Snellens/ LogMAR charts, and slit-lamp biomicroscopy for anterior segment evaluation. Further, the patients were subjected to syringing for patency of lacrimal apparatus, B scan ultrasound to rule out posterior segment pathologies, and blood tests such as estimation of Hemoglobin levels, Bleeding time, and Clotting time.

Surgery (PKP/Lamellar graft) was then planned after a detailed discussion with parents/guardians regarding the outcome and chances of repeat surgery if needed. *Preoperative Preparation:* A thorough preoperative assessment was conducted, including visual acuity tests, corneal

measurements, and an evaluation of the eye's anatomy. Children often need to be examined under general anesthesia due to a lack of cooperation. *Counseling:* Parents were counseled about the risks, benefits, and the need for long-term follow-up and amblyopia therapy. *Donor Cornea Preparation:* A suitable donor cornea was selected based on size and health. The donor cornea was trephined (cut) to the appropriate size, usually slightly larger than the recipient's corneal defect. *Recipient Eye Preparation:* The child's cornea was marked and then trephined to remove the diseased or damaged corneal tissue, creating a circular defect that matches the size of the donor tissue. *Anterior Chamber Management:* During trephination, care was taken to manage the anterior chamber, as pediatric eyes are more prone to complications like anterior segment collapse. *Graft Placement:* The donor cornea is carefully placed over the recipient's corneal bed. It was sutured in place using interrupted or continuous sutures, with meticulous attention to avoid astigmatism and ensure proper alignment. *Anterior Segment Stability:* Careful management of the anterior chamber, including avoiding vitreous prolapse, was critical. If needed, anterior vitrectomy is performed. *Intraocular Pressure Control:* Glaucoma risk is heightened in children, so intraocular pressure (IOP) was closely monitored and managed during the procedure.

The patients were prescribed a standard postoperative treatment consisting of

1. Prednisolone acetate 1% eye drops, every hour followed by down titration of dose
2. Cyclopentolate 1% w/v eye drops, 3 times a day
3. Tobramycin 0.3% w/v eye drops, 4 times a day.

Any other medications if required were added according to the patient's response and complaints. Patients follow up on 1st day, 1st week, 6th week, 3rd month, and 6th month after surgery has been documented.

Results

A total of 20 cases out of which n=11(55%) were males and n=9(45%) were females They were operated on in the given 18-month period and each case was followed up for 6 months post-surgery, patients were meticulously included after taking a detailed history and knowing the cause of corneal insult leading to opacity, all cases with congenital abnormalities of the cornea were excluded from this study. Among the 20 patients operated on, 11 were male and 9 female cases, one patient required a two-step surgery, a TKP followed by an OKP leading to a total surgery count of 21. The surgeries performed are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Chart Showing Percentage of Various Cases Performed

Table 1 presents the distribution of indications for pediatric penetrating keratoplasty (PKP) in a study of 20 cases. Acquired non-traumatic opacity was the most common indication for PKP, accounting for 35% of cases. This was followed by open globe injury (45%) and keratitis (10%). Traumatic opacities, both open and closed globe injuries, constituted 50% of cases. While present, keratoconus accounted for only 10% of cases. The

results suggest that traumatic injuries are the primary indications for pediatric PKP in this study population, with both open and closed-globe injuries contributing significantly. Acquired non-traumatic opacities, potentially related to inflammatory or degenerative conditions, were also common indications. Keratoconus, a more common indication in adult PKP, represented a smaller proportion of cases in this pediatric cohort.

Table 1: Various indications for pediatric penetrating keratoplasty in 20 cases in this study

Acquired Traumatic Opacity		Acquired Non-Traumatic Opacity	
Open Globe injury	Closed Globe Injury	Keratitis	Keratoconus
2(10%)	7(35%)	9(45%)	2(10%)

Table 2 shows the age and gender distribution of cases of Pediatric Penetrating Keratoplasty. The most affected age group was 6-10 years, accounting for 40% of cases. The youngest (1-5 years) and oldest (16-18 years) age groups had the lowest representation. There was a slight male

predominance, with males accounting for 55% of cases and females for 45%. The results suggest that the peak incidence of pediatric PKP occurs in the 6-10 year age group. While there was a slight male predominance in this study, the gender distribution was relatively equal.

Table 2: Age and Gender Distribution in Pediatric Penetrating Keratoplasty

Age Group in years	Males	Females	Total	Percentage
1 - 5	3	2	5	25
6 - 10	5	3	8	40
11 - 15	2	3	5	25
16 - 18	1	1	2	10
Total	11	9	20	100

Table 3 presents the visual outcomes of pediatric patients who underwent penetrating keratoplasty (PKP). The majority of patients (65%) experienced improved vision following PKP. A smaller proportion (20%) maintained unchanged visual acuity. A limited number of patients (15%) experienced either no assessable or worsened visual outcomes. The data suggests that PKP is generally

effective in improving visual function in pediatric patients. While a significant proportion of patients experienced improved vision, a subset of patients did not achieve the desired outcome. Factors such as the underlying cause of visual impairment, surgical complications, and postoperative management can influence visual outcomes.

Table 3: Visual Outcome of Pediatric Penetrating Keratoplasty

Visual Outcome	Frequency	Percentage
Improved	13	65
Unchanged	4	20
Not assessable	2	10
Worsened	1	5

Figure 2 depicts that in a follow-up period of 6 months: *Graft acceptance*: 60% of cases (12 out of 20) demonstrated successful graft acceptance. *Graft rejection*: 35% of cases (7 out of 20) experienced graft rejection. *Graft failure*: 5% of cases (1 out of 20) resulted in graft failure. Regarding surgical interventions, the majority of cases required a single grafting procedure. However, in a small

percentage (10%), re-grafting was necessary after an initial penetrating keratoplasty (TKP) failed, necessitating a subsequent penetrating keratoplasty (OKP). These findings highlight the challenges associated with corneal transplantation and the need for ongoing monitoring and management to optimize graft survival.

Figure 2: Graft outcomes in the cases of the study

Discussion

Corneal blindness is a significant issue in both developing and developed countries, contributing to human suffering, economic loss, and social burden. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that of the 1.5 million blind children worldwide, 70,000 suffer from active corneal involvement [3]. Ocular trauma and corneal ulceration are major, often underreported, causes of corneal blindness, leading to 1.5 to 2 million new cases of monocular blindness annually [4]. Infectious keratitis is a leading cause of preventable and treatable monocular blindness in the developing world. Childhood blindness (approximately 1.5 million globally, with 5 million visually disabled) is caused by conditions like xerophthalmia (350,000 cases annually), ophthalmia neonatorum, measles [5], and less common diseases such as herpes simplex infections and vernal keratoconjunctivitis [4]. Congenital corneal disorders are significant causes of childhood blindness, occurring either in isolation, in combination or as part of a syndrome. Corneal opacification in early life can lead to long-term changes in the central nervous system [1]. Our study excludes congenital opacities (CHED/Non-

CHED). Keratoconus, a non-inflammatory ectatic disorder, results in a cone-shaped cornea due to stromal thinning. Typically starting at puberty and progressing into the 3rd or 4th decade, early symptoms may include mild refractive errors, eventually progressing to visual distortion and loss due to irregular astigmatism. Clinical signs include stromal thinning, Munson's sign, Rizutti's phenomenon, Vogt's striae, Fleischer's ring, and stromal scarring [6]. Diagnosis can be aided by retro illumination, retinoscopic reflex scissoring, and "Charleux" oil droplet tests, alongside videokeratography, keratometry, and pachymetry. Sudden visual loss may occur due to hydrops formation. Management includes both conservative (topical steroids, cycloplegics, hyperosmotic agents, systemic analgesics) and surgical approaches, such as intracameral injections of SF6 or C3F8.

Early treatment includes refractive error correction and contact lenses. Corneal collagen cross-linking with riboflavin and intrastromal corneal ring segments has shown promise. Advanced cases may require keratoplasty or excimer laser phototherapeutic keratectomy. In our study, 10% of cases were diagnosed with keratoconus, and deep

anterior lamellar keratoplasty was performed. Both cases had 100% graft acceptance with no postoperative complications. Penetrating injuries remain a significant cause of acquired corneal scarring in children, leading to tissue loss, anterior segment distortion, and corneal decompensation, often requiring keratoplasty [1]. The primary concern in pediatric keratoplasty for trauma is the risk of amblyopia, making early surgery crucial to prevent visual deprivation. Our study found that 45% of cases had acquired traumatic corneal opacification, with 10% resulting from open-globe injuries and 35% from closed-globe injuries. In Western nations, herpes simplex keratitis is a common cause of corneal scarring in children under six, whereas, in developing countries, infectious keratitis and post-infectious corneal scars are the main causes of pediatric corneal morbidity. Vitamin A deficiency-related keratomalacia, a preventable cause of corneal opacification, leads to xerosis, keratinized plaques, stromal ulcers, and melting [7]. However, we did not encounter such cases in our study.

Childhood keratitis, though less common than adult keratitis [8], presents unique diagnostic and treatment challenges. Children may be uncooperative, and incomplete or misleading histories can delay treatment, increasing the risk of blindness and amblyopia. Trauma is the most common predisposing factor for pediatric microbial keratitis [9-13]. Other key factors include systemic illness, prior ocular surgery (e.g., congenital glaucoma surgery), malnutrition, and increased colonization at birth. Contact lens wear has recently emerged as a major factor among adolescents [3]. Corneal trauma can range from minor abrasions by foreign bodies to damage from tear insufficiency, malnutrition, or contact lenses. Contamination with vegetable matter is a leading cause of traumatic keratitis cases [8].

Age-related risk factors common in adults, such as tear film dysfunction, external ocular disease, lid abnormalities, and neurotrophic or exposure keratitis, play a smaller role in children [11]. The specific inflammatory responses in pediatric microbial keratitis are not fully understood, but cytokines and polymorphonuclear leukocytes likely play significant roles, similar to adult cases. Bacterial keratitis is the most common form, followed by mixed bacterial and fungal infections [9]. Children often present with severe ocular pain, redness, photophobia, and excessive tearing. Early diagnosis is critical for effective treatment and visual rehabilitation. Treatment aims to eliminate the infection, reduce inflammation, prevent corneal damage, and promote healing. Antibiotics, both topical and systemic, are essential. Cycloplegics, such as atropine 1% ointment, should be used due to the strong ciliary muscle tone in children.

For corneal perforations, small ones may be managed with fibrin or cyanoacrylate glue, while larger perforations often require corneal patch grafts or therapeutic penetrating keratoplasty (TPK). In our study, 10% of cases required TPK, with patients undergoing OKP after infection was controlled. Khvatova AV et al. [14] reported graft survival rates of 71%, 61%, and approximately 55% at 1, 2, and 5 years post-surgery, respectively, which aligns with our study's 60% graft survival at 6 months. Additionally, they found visual acuity improvement in 54% of cases post-operatively, no change or worsening in 22%, and unassessable in 24%. In our study, visual acuity improved in 65% of cases, remained unchanged in 20%, was unassessable in 10%, and worsened in 5%. Yang LL et al. [15] documented a 56% probability of maintaining a clear graft at 6 months, comparable to our finding of 60%. Similarly, Beltaief et al. [16], with a mean follow-up of 41.8 months, observed 83.3% clear grafts, 4 cases of graft rejection, and 3 cases of graft failure (16.6%). Our study showed similar results: 60% clear grafts, 35% graft rejection, and 5% graft failure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, penetrating keratoplasty is still the best operation that can be done in children with corneal opacities and ectasias because there are no other options available. Even though the process gives low potential for graft rejection and an average amount of vision enhancement, timely intervention, professional surgery, and adequate post-operative treatment can contribute much to positive results. Of the subjects under investigation, 65% of them had their vision acuity increased after six months, indicating the advantages of keratoplasty. However, there are issues such as amblyopia and postoperative astigmatism that still present significant barriers to success. This is why these complications should be treated as soon as possible and as intensively as possible, including the use of preservative-free topical steroids for managing graft rejection. Furthermore, delicate concerns such as damaged or insecure sutures prevent graft rejection and vascularization. In conclusion, pediatric keratoplasty is a safe procedure with a good prognosis and therefore serves as the primary form of treatment for specific corneal diseases in children if managed properly.

References

1. Vanathi M, Panda A, Vengayil S, Chaudhuri Z, Dada T. Pediatric keratoplasty. *Surv Ophthalmol.* 2009 Mar-Apr;54(2):245-71.
2. Sharma A, Sharma R. Pediatric Corneal Transplant Surgery: Challenges for Successful Outcome. *Nepal J Ophthalmol.* 2019 Jul;11(22):197-210.

3. Whitcher JP, Srinivasan M, Upadhyay MP. Corneal blindness: A global perspective. *Bull World Health Organ* 2001;79(3):214-21.
4. Singh G, Palanisamy M, Madhavan B, Rajaraman R, Narendran K, Kour A, Venkatapathy N. Multivariate Analysis of Childhood Microbial Keratitis in South India. *Ann Acad Med Singapore* 2006;35:185-89.
5. Foster A, Sommer A. Childhood blindness from corneal ulceration in Africa: Causes, prevention, and treatment. *Bull WHO* 1986;64: 61 9-23.
6. Rabinowitz YS. Keratoconus. *Surv Ophthalmol* 1998;42:297-319.
7. Sommer A. Xerophthalmia, keratomalacia, and nutritional blindness. *Int Ophthalmol* 1990;14: 195-99.
8. Cruz OA, Sabir SM, Capo H, Alfonso EC. Microbial keratitis in childhood. *Ophthalmology* 1993;100:192-6.
9. Parmar P, Salman A, Kalavathy CM, et al. Microbial keratitis in the extreme of ages. *Cornea*. 2006;25;153-8.
10. Kunitomo DY, Sharma S, Reddy MK, Gopinathan U, Jyothi J, Miller D, et al. Microbial keratitis in children. *Ophthalmology* 1998;105 :252-7.
11. Ormerod LD, Murphree AL, Gomez DS, Schanzlin DJ, Smith RE. Microbial keratitis in children. *Ophthalmology* 1986;93:449-55.
12. Vajpayee RB, Ray M, Panda A, Sharma N, Taylor HR, Murthy GV, Satpathy G, Pandey RM. Risk factors for pediatric presumed microbial keratitis: a case-control study. *Cornea* 1999;18:565-9.
13. Bharathi MJ, Ramakrishnan R, Meenakshi R, Padmavathy S, Shivakumar C, Srinivasan M. Microbial keratitis in South India: influence of risk factors, climate, and geographical variation. *Ophthalmic Epidemiol* 2007;14(2):61-9.
14. Khvatova AV, Pleskova AV. Opyt skvoznoĭ keratoplastiki u detei: vyzhivaemost' transplantation, funktsional'nye rezul'taty, faktory riska [Experience in penetrating keratoplasty in children: graft survival, functional results, and risk factors]. *Vestn Oftalmol.* 2003 SepOct; 119(5):3-7. (Article in Russian).
15. Yang LL, Lambert SR, Lynn MJ, Stulting RD. Long-term results of corneal graft survival in infants and children with peters anomaly. *Ophthalmology*. 1999 Apr;106(4):833-48. doi: 10.1016/S0161- 6420(99)90175-76.
16. Beltaief O, Farah H, Kamoun R, Ben Said A, Ouertani A. La greffe de cornée chez l'enfant [Penetrating keratoplasty in children]. *Tunis Med.* 2003 Jul;81(7):477-81. (Article in French).